

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et, al. 2025)

Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree Oil for Internal Combustion Engine

MANI, Suleiman¹

abuljaafar12@gmail.com

08034950954

ABDULRAHMAN, Umar²

aumar5k5@gmail.com

08051777636

MUHAMMAD, Fatima Dandare¹

fatimadandare@gmail.com

08060706591

¹Department of Chemistry, Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, Sokoto

²Department of Chemistry, Shehu Shagari University of Education, Sokoto

Correspondence: aumar5k5@gmail.com +2348051777636

Abstract

The current challenges of fossil fuels have led to the need for alternative energy sources like biodiesel and biodiesel blends because they are renewable and environmentally friendly. This study investigates biodiesel production using neem oil as a feedstock that involved, oil extraction, moisture/FFA reduction then base transesterification reaction using the extracted neem seed oil. The physico-chemical and fuel properties of the neem seed oil biodiesel was analysed using standard analytical procedures. The effects of some operating variables were ascertained and its combustion performance was assessed in an internal combustion engine. The results reveal the optimum conditions for biodiesel production to be ratio 1:6 of oil to methanol and 1.5 h reaction time. The viscosity at this condition was 5.53 cSt. The same procedure was repeated for NaOCH₃ catalyst concentrations of 0.5, 0.75, 1 and 1.25%. The lowest viscosity of 6.79 cSt was recorded at both 1 and 1.25% catalyst concentrations. The fuel properties of the biodiesel compared favourably with the recommendation by the American Standard Testing Method. The emissions of different blends showed that neem biodiesel has lower emissions of CO and NO than petrol diesel but higher NO_x. Thus, neem oil as non-edible oil can be a good renewable raw material for biodiesel production in diesel engines and plants with little or no modification.

Keywords: *Neem tree oil, transesterification, biodiesel, internal Combustion*

Introduction

Fossil fuels are non-renewable energy resources. Although, these fuels are contributing largely to the world energy supply, their production and use have raised environmental concerns, (Wang et al., 2011). It has been shown that 98% of carbon emissions result from fossil fuel combustion (Balat and Balat, 2010). According to Shay (1993), the continued and increasing use of petroleum diesel intensifies air pollution and magnifies the global warming problem caused by CO₂ and other particulate matters. The growing demand for fuel and the increasing concern for the environment due

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et. al. 2025)

to the use of fossil fuel have led to the increasing popularity of biodiesel as a useful alternative and environmentally friendly energy resource (Ma and Hanna, 1999). Its advantages over petroleum diesel based on its safety, renewability and biodegradability have been reviewed widely (Demirbas, 2007; Fukuda et al., 2001; Knothe, 2006). Although, both have similar properties and performance parameters (Table 1), its non-sulphur content makes it a preferred alternative.

Biodiesel fuel is presently attracting increasing attention worldwide as a blending component or a direct replacement for diesel fuel in vehicle engines (Demirba, 2009). When blended with diesel fuel the designation BXX indicates the XX% amount of biodiesel in the blend, for example B30 is 30% biodiesel and 70% diesel. It has been reported that blends up to B20 can be used in nearly all diesel equipment and are compatible with most storage and distribution equipment (Balat, 2011). These low-level blends generally do not require any engine modifications. However, higher blends or B100 can be used in many engines built with little or no modification (Demirbas, 2007). The presence of oxygen in biodiesel ($\approx 10\%$) improves combustion and reduces CO, soot, and hydrocarbon emissions while slightly increasing the NO_x emissions. Fukuda et al. (2001) showed that using B20 in trucks and buses would completely eliminate the black smoke released during acceleration. Although, biodiesel is gaining popularity, more than 95% of the renewable resources used for its production are edible oils (Gui et al., 2008), which will in a long term have serious implications on food availability and the cost of biodiesel as it may be more expensive than petroleum diesel.

Table 1: Petroleum Diesel versus Biodiesel

Fuel Property	Diesel	Biodiesel
Fuel standard	ASTM D975	ASTM D6751
Fuel composition	C10-C21 HC ^b	C12-C22 FAME ^c
Kinematic viscosity, mm ² /s (at 40 °C)	1.3 – 4.1	1.9 – 6.0
Specific gravity	0.85	0.88
Boiling point, °C	188–343	182 – 338
Flash point, °C	60 – 80	100 –170
Cloud point, °C	-15 to 5	-3 to 12
Pour point, °C	-35 to –15	-15 to 10
Cetane number (ignition quality)	40 – 55	48 – 65
Stoichiometric air/fuel ratio (AFR)	15	13.8

Source: Aransiola et al (2011)

Table 2: Fatty Acid Composition of Neem Tree Oil

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et. al. 2025)

Fatty acid	Formula	Systemic name	Structure	Wt (%)
Palmitic	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	Hexadecanoic	16:0	18.1
Stearic	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	Octadecanoic	18:0	18.1
Oleic	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	cis-9-Octadecenoic	18:1	44.5
Linoleic	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	cis-9,cis-12-Octadecenoic	18:2	18.3
Linolenic	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂	cis-6,cis-9,cis-12-Octadecatrienoic	18:3	0.2
Arachidic	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O ₂	Eicosanoic	20:0	0.8
Total Saturated Fatty Acid	37%			
Total Mono – unsaturated Fatty Acid	44.5%			
Total Poly – unsaturated Fatty Acid	18.5			

Source: Martin et al. (2010)

Current studies on this subject have focused on the use of non-edible oils from plants with the view to addressing the aforementioned concerns. There are vast numbers of non-edible oil plants in nature; these include neem (*A. indica*), jatropha tree (*J. curcas*), karanja (*P. pinnata*), tobacco seed (*N. tabacum* L.), rice bran, mahua (*M. indica*), rubber plant (*H. brasiliensis*), castor, linseed, and microalgae (Demirbas, 2011). *Jatropha curcas* oil plants have been widely studied with respect to biodiesel production from non-edible oils (Berchmans and Hirata, 2008; Jain and Sharma, 2010; Lu et al., 2009; Raja et al., 2011) however, limited studies exist on the neem oil plant (Muthu et al., 2010; Ragit et al., 2011). The neem oil plant is a fast growing plant with long productive life span of 150 to 200 years, its ability to survive on drought and poor soils at a very hot temperature of 44°C and a low temperature of up to 4°C has been reported (Karmakar et al., 2011), and its high oil content of 39.7 to 60% (Martin et al., 2010; Narwal et al., 1997). A mature neem tree produces 30 to 50 kg fruit every year (Karmakar et al. 2011). It contains a high percentage of monounsaturated fatty acids (C16:1, C18:1), a low proportion of polyunsaturated acids (C18:2, C18:3) and a controlled amount of saturated fatty acids (C16:0, C18:0) (Wang et al., 2011). The aforementioned characteristics of neem oil plants and its fatty acid composition of the oil make it to be a useful renewable source for biodiesel production (Aransiola et al, 2011).

The basic reaction involved in the production of bio diesel (also called fatty acid methyl esters, FAME) is not new and has been reviewed in the literatures (Fukuda et al., 2001; Kusdiana and Saka, 2001; Ma and Hanna, 1999; Schuchardt et al., 1998)–reaction between triglycerides with methanol in the presence of a strong base as a catalyst yielding the desired FAME and a by product, glycerol (Patil and Deng, 2009; Tsai et al., 2007; Keera et al., 2011). It has been reported that the triglycerides used in alkaline transesterification reactions should contain not more than 1% free fatty acids (FFA), which is equivalent to 2 mg KOH/g triglyceride, otherwise saponification reaction will hinder separation of the ester from glycerine thereby reducing the yield and formation rate of FAME. Mittelbach (1996), Zhang et al. (2003) and Berrios (2007). A two-step acid–base catalyzed transesterification reaction has been shown to be appropriate for biodiesel production from neem oil due to its high FFA (32.538 mg KOH/g)

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et. al. 2025)

(Berchmans and Hirata, 2008; Wang et al. 2011; Jain and Sharma, 2010; Liu et al., 2010), the pre-treatment of the oil is critical before the alkaline transesterification.

The aim of this study was to investigate the production of biodiesel from neem oil with a view to determine its performance in Internal Combustion engine (I.C. engine). The physicochemical properties of the biodiesel produced were measured with time and the emissions released from various blends in an internal combustion were determined. The results of this study would form a basis for the development of a biodiesel production from Neem tree oil, especially in Nigeria where this feedstock is in abundance.

Statement of the Research Problem

Nigeria faces increasing demand for energy, especially in the transportation and power generation sectors, leading to high dependency on fossil fuels which are costly, non-renewable, and environmentally harmful. With growing environmental concerns and fluctuating petroleum prices, there is a pressing need to explore sustainable, locally available, and eco-friendly alternatives to diesel fuel. Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), an abundant and non-edible oil-bearing tree in many parts of Nigeria, offers potential as a feedstock for biodiesel production. However, there is limited local research on the fuel properties, engine performance, and emissions of biodiesel derived from neem oil. Understanding these characteristics is essential for assessing its viability as an alternative fuel for internal combustion engines and promoting energy diversification.

Objectives of the Study

- i. To extract and produce biodiesel from neem tree oil using transesterification.
- ii. To characterize the physicochemical properties of the produced biodiesel (e.g., viscosity, density, flash point, cetane number, calorific value, etc.).
- iii. To evaluate the compatibility and performance of neem-based biodiesel in a standard internal combustion engine.
- iv. To compare the performance and emission characteristics of neem biodiesel with conventional diesel.

Research Questions

- i. Can neem seed oil be effectively converted into biodiesel through transesterification?
- ii. What are the key physicochemical properties of neem biodiesel?
- iii. How does neem biodiesel compare with conventional diesel in terms of fuel quality?
- iv. Is neem biodiesel suitable for use in internal combustion engines?

Research Hypothesis

H₀₁: Neem oil can be efficiently converted into biodiesel using the transesterification process.

H₀₂: The physicochemical properties of neem biodiesel meet the standard specifications for biodiesel fuels.

H₀₃: Neem biodiesel exhibits comparable or improved performance characteristics relative to conventional diesel.

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et, al. 2025)

Ho: Neem biodiesel is suitable for application in internal combustion engines without causing adverse effects on engine operation.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection

Neem seed (*Azadirachta indica*) were collected from the botanical garden of the Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Sokoto State, Nigeria. It was identified according to the flora of West Africa in the Herbarium Unit of the University where vouchers of each specimen were deposited. Petroleum diesel was procured from the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) Mega filling station, along Gusau road Sokoto.

Sample Preparation

The neem seeds were sun-dried and the shells were manually cracked to obtain the kernels. The kernels were then milled and stored at 4°C until needed for further analysis. All the chemicals used such as Methanol, Sodium methoxide, anhydrous Calcium chloride, sulphuric acid, sodium thiosulphate etc. were analytical grades.

Oil Extraction

Oils from the milled seeds was exhaustively extracted with a Soxhlet apparatus using methanol as the solvent after which it was subjected to physico-chemical characterization using standard analytical methods on the appearance, viscosity, specific gravity, density, and FFA values, flash, pour and cloud points, pour point as reported in AOAC (2000) and AOCS. (2003).

Biodiesel Production

The oil was heated in an oven at 100-120 °C for 20 min to reduce moisture/water concentration below 5 g/kg. The mechanism of reduction in free fatty acid was adopted for oils containing FFA up to 20%, by lowering the acid value, making 300 cm³ of oil used to contain FFA less than 1%. This was done by adding sufficient sodium hydroxide in 700 g/L aqueous solution, heating at 30-35 °C to precipitate the solids and allowing to settle overnight. The clear oil was decanted and the FFA determined according to ISO EN660, (1996).

Two-step acid-base catalysed transesterification

Crude neem oil when transesterified using NaOH catalyst produced a significant number of soaps from saponification side reaction. This was due to the high level of free fatty acids and small quantity of moisture in the crude neem oil. Therefore, a two-step process acid-catalysed esterification followed by alkali catalysed transesterification was employed according to the method of Berchmans and Hirata (2008).

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et. al. 2025)

Acid pre-treatment (acid catalysed esterification)

The crude oil was weighed, heated at 60°C for about 10 minutes and mixed with 55.8 ml of methanol (60%w/w of oil). 1.2%w/w of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added to the mixture. The resulting mixture was then stirred on magnetic hot plate for 1 hour at 50°C, after which it was allowed to settle for 2 hours. The pre-treated oil was separated from the methanol-water phase at the top.

Base-catalysed transesterification

These laboratory scale experiments were carried out batch wise in a 250 ml conical flask containing 40 g of pre-treated neem oil. These were done on a magnetic stirrer at temperature of 60°C, keeping the agitation rate constant at 400 rpm for oil to alcohol ratio of 1:4, 1:5, 1:6 and 1:7. The pre-treated oil was poured into the reaction flask and heated. A solution of NaOH in methanol (1%) was dissolved at room temperature and the pre-treated oil was added. The reaction was allowed to run for various periods of 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 hours. The reaction condition of 60°C and 1% NaOH catalyst was maintained as reported (Aransiola et al., 2010; Muthu et al., 2010).

The resulting mixture was poured into a separating funnel and allowed to settle under gravity for 24 hours for separation of biodiesel. The lower glycerol layer was tapped off after which the biodiesel layer was washed with warm water three to four times and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. The viscosity value was used a proxy measure of the extent of reaction with reference to ASTM standard which served as an indicator of the reaction being completed. This approach has been used in the literatures (Aransiola et al., 2010; Belewu et al., 2010; Fukuda et al., 2001). This procedure was repeated using sodium methoxide with a view to explore the effect of other readily available catalyst on biodiesel yield. Different catalyst ratios of 0.5, 0.75, 1 and 1.25% were used, keeping rate of agitation, temperature and reaction time constant at 250 rpm, 60°C and 1.5 hours, respectively. This variation of Sodium methoxide catalyst was carried out because it is not commonly used as Sodium hydroxide catalyst. The biodiesel produced were analysed for the following parameters: pour point, flash points, cloud points, Specific gravity at 15°C, water content, colour, density, and kinematic viscosity at 40°C.

Chemical Analysis

Physicochemical Analysis

The oil was analysed for some physicochemical properties (iodine value, saponification value, acid value) by methods described by the association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 1984; Aransiola et al., 2010).

Characterization of biodiesel

The characterization of the biodiesel was carried out according to the methods used by Aransiola et al. (2010). The density and the viscosity were measured at room temperature using the density bottle and the Brooke auto viscometer (DV-I PRIME, Brookfield, USA), respectively. The parameters were determined with the standard methods.

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et, al. 2025)

Investigation of Biodiesel on Internal Combustion Engine

The investigations on the combustion characteristics of the conventional diesel, neem methyl ester (B100) and its blends were conducted on a single cylinder one-stroke 165F jet diesel engine having a rated output of 3.23 kW at 2600 rpm. This was fuelled with prepared test fuels. The emissions (CO, NO_x and NO) were measured through an automatic EGA4 palm top flue gas analyser having Ni-MH rechargeable battery.

Results and Discussion

The physical and chemical properties of the neem oil are presented in Table 3. These properties compared favourably with literature values (Muthu et al., 2010; Ragit et al., 2011). The relative degree of unsaturation of a fat or oil is determined by its iodine number. The results suggests that neem oil possess certain degree of unsaturation as reported by Martin (2010). An iodine number of 81.28 obtained in this study falls within the range of 30 (reported for butter which is known to be saturated) and 101 for corn oil –a polyunsaturated feedstock (Ramos et al., 2009). It should be noted that the higher the number of double bonds, the higher the iodine number. As discussed earlier, oils high in monounsaturations level are good sources of biodiesel production. The high saponification and high acid values found in neem oil are common to most non edible oils used for biodiesel production (Veljkovic et al., 2006; Zhang and Jiang, 2008). These results suggest neem oil as an ideal choice for biodiesel production. After acid pre-treatment, the oil acid value reduced to less than 2 mgKOH/g and its colour became lighter. This makes it fit for the alkali transesterification process (Berrios et al., 2007; Ghadge and Raheman, 2006; Veljkovic et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2011). The viscosity of the oil reduced after transesterification from 43.75 to 5.53 cSt likewise the density from 0.9182 to 0.8762 g/ml, which is acceptable as per ASTM recommendation for biodiesel.

Effect of Reaction Time and Oil to Alcohol Ratio on the Transesterification of Neem Oil

Base catalysed transesterification is preferred over acid catalysed transesterification reactions for the production of biodiesel at industrial level because it provides better conversion rates and efficiencies (Fukuda et al., 2001). The basic parameter reflecting the extent of the reaction could be the viscosity, since it is directly related with the fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) content of the product and is one of the specifications to comply with in biodiesel production (Shu et al., 2007). In this study therefore, the effectiveness and completion of the ester conversion process is shown as the variation of the viscosity with reaction time at various oil to alcohol ratio investigated (Table 4).

Table 4: Effect of reaction time on oil to alcohol ratio on kinematic viscosity of the transesterification of neem oil

Time (h)	Viscosity (cSt)				
	Oil: Methanol Ration	1:4	1:5	1:6	1:7
0.1		5.7	5.62	5.56	5.55
1		5.65	5.58	5.54	5.53
1.5		5.6	5.54	5.53	5.51
2		5.58	5.53	5.51	5.51

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et, al. 2025)

The viscosity of the neem methyl ester decreases as the oil to alcohol ratio and reaction time are increasing. Aransiola et al. (2010) investigated the transesterification of soybean oil and showed that viscosity decreases with increasing reaction time and temperature. Similar study on biodiesel production from used vegetable oil also revealed that viscosity of the product obtained diminishes with reaction temperature and also decreases with increased space time in the reactor (Brito et al., 2007). The lowest viscosity obtained in this study was 5.51 cSt at oil-to-alcohol ratios of 1:6 and 1:7 and reaction times of 1.5 hours and 2 hours. From economic point of view, ratio 1:6 is preferred to 1:7 as it minimizes amount of methanol used in the process. On the other hand, the reaction time of 1.5 hour is preferred to 2 hours since there is no significant difference in the biodiesel parameters (Figures 2 and 3) beyond 1.5 hour. Although it may be argued that the reaction completed within 30 min due to comparatively similar viscosity values; it has been shown previously that the FAME yield increased significantly for reaction time greater than 1 hour (Aransiola, 2010). For this study therefore, the optimum oil to alcohol ratio and reaction time are taken to be 1:6 and 1.5 hours, respectively. This is in agreement with the established literatures (Balat and Balat, 2010; Fukuda et al., 2001; Lu et al., 2009; Ragit et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2011).

Effect of Catalyst Variation using Sodium Methoxide on the Density and Viscosity of the Neem Methyl Ester

The results of the viscosity and density of neem methyl ester using sodium methoxide concentration are presented in Figure 1. This was conducted at the optimum conditions obtained previously. The results show that as the percentage concentration of the sodium methoxide catalyst increases, there is corresponding decrease in the values of both density and viscosity. The lowest viscosity of 6.79 cSt was recorded at both 1 and 1.25% catalyst concentrations while the lowest density of 878.4 g/l was recorded at 1.25% catalyst concentrations but the density value at 1% catalyst concentration was also very close (878.6 g/l).

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et, al. 2025)

Figure 1: Variation of viscosity and density with sodium methoxide catalyst concentration.

Figure 2: Variation of Density using NaOH catalyst with reaction time

The result shows that biodiesel produced using NaOH catalyst (5.53 cSt) is better than that obtained using sodium methoxide at the same operating conditions. A drop of the biodiesel from NaOH catalyst is smaller than that from methoxide catalyst as a smaller amount of the fuel is desired in engine combustion chamber for complete combustion to occur.

Figure 3: Variation of Flash point with Reaction Time using NaOH Catalyst

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et, al. 2025)

Figure 4: The Plot of different Blends of Neem oil Biodiesel and Diesel against CO, NO, and NO_x emissions

Fuel Properties of the Neem Methyl Ester

The density, cloud point and flash point of the neem methyl ester using sodium hydroxide as the catalyst at the optimum conditions (Temperature of 60°C and oil to alcohol ratio of 1:6) were studied with reaction time. These are shown in Figures 2 and 3. Both flash and cloud points decreased significantly with increase in the reaction time, however, beyond the reaction time of 1.5 hours these parameters appear to be constant. Therefore, it is reasonable to terminate the transesterification reaction at 1.5 hour. Fuels above flash point of 66°C are considered safe fuel (Raja et al., 2011) and are suitable for all climatic conditions, while fuels with higher cloud points can affect engine performance and emission adversely under cold climatic conditions.

Table: 5 Fuel Properties of Neem Oil Biodiesel

Property	Neem Oil Biodiesel	Biodiesel Standard	Test Method
Kinematic Viscosity	5.53	1.9 – 6.0	ASTMD-445
Flash Point (°C)	150	130(min)	ASTMD-93
Cloud Point (°C)	6	-	ASTMD-2500
Pour Point (°C)	3	-	ASTMD-97
Moisture Content	-	0.050max	ASTMD-2709
Specific Gravity (15/15°C)	0.8762	0.860 – 0.900	-

The fuel properties obtained at the reaction condition is in agreement with the ASTM biodiesel standard. The density, cloud point and flash point at the optimum conditions at reaction time of 1.5 hour are 0.8765 g/ml, 6.0 and 150°C, respectively. Other fuel properties like colour, water content and pour point were characterized at the optimum conditions to be 1.0, 0 and 3.0, respectively. These properties compared favourably with the acceptable biodiesel standards and are presented in Table 5.

2 Investigation of biodiesel on internal combustion engines Experimental investigation was carried out for different blends of neem oil biodiesel and the emissions (CO, NO, NO_x) were evaluated and compared with conventional diesel. The results for the various emission data generated are presented

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et, al. 2025)

in Figure 4. The results show that biodiesel gave a less carbon monoxide (CO) compared to petroleum diesel. The emissions of CO and NO were found to be decreasing with biodiesel blends. The minimum and maximum reduction of CO was 8.32 and 41.32%, while that of NO was 14.51 and 37.74% respectively as compared to diesel. The emissions of NO_x increased with the biodiesel blends. The percentage increment between B100 and diesel was 10.74%. Similar trends of observations on CO, NO and NO_x production were also reported while running the diesel engines with karanja, neem, Honge, Jatropha and sesame oil methyl esters (Banapurmath and Tewari, 2009; Nabi, 2006; Raheman and Phadatare, 2004).

Conclusion

In this study, production of biodiesel from crude neem oil with high acid value was investigated. The effect of some operating variables were investigated and its performance was assessed in an internal combustion engine. The fatty acid methyl ester from neem oil was produced by two step acid-base transesterification process. The first step reduced the acid level to less than 2 mgKOH/g. The second step converted it to fatty acid methyl ester using 1% NaOH catalyst. Viscosity of 5.53 cSt was obtained at the optimum oil to alcohol ratio and reaction time of 1:6 and 1.5 h, respectively. When sodium methoxide catalyst was used, the lowest viscosity of 6.79 cSt was recorded at both 1 and 1.25% catalyst concentrations while the lowest density of 878.4 g/l was recorded at 1.25% catalyst concentrations. The emissions of CO and NO decreased with the biodiesel blends while that of NO_x increased. The properties of the biodiesel produced in this study compared favourably with the values prescribed by American Standard Testing Method. The results obtained in this study would be relevant in the development of biodiesel production from neem oil especially in Nigeria where this feedstock is abundant.

Recommendations

- i. Governments and environmental agencies should promote the cultivation and use of non-edible oil seeds like neem for biofuel development.
- ii. Further studies should be conducted to investigate long-term engine performance, emission profiles, and blending ratios of neem biodiesel.
- iii. Small- and medium-scale neem biodiesel production units could be developed in rural areas to boost energy access and economic development.
- iv. Awareness campaigns should highlight the environmental and economic benefits of biodiesel from indigenous resources like neem.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et, al. 2025)

Authors wish to thank The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) for the research grant under the Institution-Based Research (IBR) to undertake this research and the Federal College of Education (FCE) Gidan Madi for the Laboratory space to conduct this research.

REFERENCES

- AOAC (1984). Official Method of Analysis. J. Assoc. Off. Anal. Chem. Washington.
- AOAC (2000). Official methods of Analysis of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists, 11, 15th edition, sec. 985.29. The Association Arlington, VA
- AOAC (2005). Official Methods of Analysis of the Association of official Analytical Chemists, 16th Edition, Washington DC30033
- AOCS (2003). Official Methods of the American Oil Chemists' Society, 3rd Edition, Champaign, Illinois
- Aransiola E, Betiku E, Layokun S, Solomon B (2010). Production of biodiesel by transesterification of refined soybean oil. Int. J. Biol. Chem. Sci. 4(2): 391-399.
- Aransiola EF (2010). Kinetics of the conversion of soy bean oil and Jatropha curcas oil to biodiesel. in: Chemical Engineering, PhD Thesis, Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife. Ile-Ife, Nigeria.
- Aransiola, E. F., Betiku, E., Ikhuimorgbe, D. I. O and Ojumu, T. V. (2011). Production of Biodiesel from crude neem oil feedstock and its Emission from internal combustion Engines. African Journal of Biotechnology, 11(22): 6178-6186.
- Balat M, Balat H (2010). Progress in Biodiesel Processing. Appl. Energ. 87(6): 1815-1835.
- Balat M (2011). Potential alternatives to edible oils for biodiesel production - A review of current work. Energ. Convers Manage. 52(2), 1479-1492.
- Banapurmath N, Tewari P (2009). Comparative performance studies of a 4-stroke CI engine operated on dual fuel mode with producer gas and Honge oil and its methyl ester (HOME) with and without carburetor. Renew Energ. 34(4): 1009-1015.
- Belewu M, Adekola FA, Adebayo GB, Ameen OM, Muhammed NO, Olaniyan AM, Adekola OF, Musa AK (2010). Physico-chemical characteristics of oil and biodiesel from Nigerian and Indian Jatropha curcas seeds. Int. J. Biol. Chem. Sci. 4(2): 524-529.
- Berchmans HJ, Hirata S (2008). Biodiesel production from crude Jatropha curcas L. seed oil with a high content of free fatty acids. Bioresour. Technol. 99(6): 1716-1721.
- Berrios M, Siles J, Martin M, Martin A (2007). A kinetic study of the esterification of free fatty acids (FFA) in sunflower oil. Fuel, 86(15): 2383-2388.
- Brito A, Borges M, Otero N (2007). Zeolite Y as a heterogeneous catalyst in biodiesel fuel production from used vegetable oil. Energ. Fuel, 21(6): 3280-3283.

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et. al. 2025)

- Demirba A (2009). Production of biodiesel from algae oils, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects. *Energ. Source*, 31(2): 163-168.
- Demirbas A (2011). Biodiesel from oilgae, biofixation of carbon dioxide by microalgae: A solution to pollution problems. *Appl. Energ.* 88: 3541-3547.
- Demirbas A (2007). Importance of biodiesel as transportation fuel. *Energ. Policy*, 35(9): 4661-4670.
- Fukuda H, Kondo A, Noda H (2001). Biodiesel fuel production by transesterification of oils. *J. Biosci. Bioeng.* 92(5): 405-416.
- Ghadge SV, Raheman H (2006). Process optimization for biodiesel production from mahua (*Madhuca indica*) oil using response surface methodology. *Bioresour. Technol.* 97(3): 379-384.
- Gui M, Lee K, Bhatia S (2008). Feasibility of edible oil vs. non-edible oil vs. waste edible oil as biodiesel feedstock. *Energy*, 33(11): 1646-1653.
- Jain S, Sharma M (2010). Kinetics of acid base catalyzed transesterification of *Jatropha curcas* oil. *Bioresour. Technol.* 101(20): 7701-7706.
- Kiss AA, Dimian AC, Rothenberg G (2008). Biodiesel by catalytic reactive distillation powered by metal oxides. *Energ. Fuel*, 22(1): 598-604.
- Knothe G (2006). Analyzing biodiesel: standards and other methods. *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.* 83(10), 823-833.
- Kusdiana D, Saka S (2001). Kinetics of transesterification in rapeseed oil to biodiesel fuel as treated in supercritical methanol. *Fuel*, 80(5): 693-698.
- Lu H, Liu Y, Zhou H, Yang Y, Chen M, Liang B (2009). Production of biodiesel from *Jatropha curcas* L. oil. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 33(5): 1091-1096.
- Ma F, Hanna MA (1999). Biodiesel production: a review1. *Bioresour. Technol.* 70(1): 1-15.
- Martín C, Moure A, Martín G, Carrillo E, Domínguez H, Parajó JC (2010). Fractional Characterisation of *Jatropha*, *Neem*, *Moringa*, *Trisperma*, *Castor* and *Candlenut* Seeds as Potential Feedstocks for Biodiesel Production in Cuba. *Biomass Bioenerg.* 34(4): 533-538.
- Mittelbach M (1996). Diesel fuel derived from vegetable oils, VI: Specifications and quality control of biodiesel. *Bioresour. Technol.* 56(1): 7-11.
- Muthu H, SathyaSelvabala V, Varathachary T, Kirupha Selvaraj D, Nandagopal J, Subramanian S (2010). Synthesis of biodiesel from *Neem* oil using sulfated zirconia via transesterification. *Braz. J. Chem. Eng.* 27(4): 601-608.
- Nabi M (2006). Improvement of engine emissions with conventional diesel fuel and diesel-biodiesel blends. *Bioresour. Technol.* 97(3): 372-378.
- Oniya, O.O. and Bamgboye, A.I. (2014). Production of biodiesel from groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*, L.) oil. *Agricultural Engineering International: CIGR Journal*, 16(1), 143-150.

(Production and Characterization of Biodiesel from Neem Tree ... Mani, S. Et. al. 2025)

- Ragit SS, Mohapatra SK, Kundu K, Gill P (2011). Optimization of neem methyl ester from transesterification process and fuel characterization as a diesel substitute. *Biomass Bioenerg.* 35(3): 1138-1144.
- Raheman H, Phadatare A (2004). Diesel engine emissions and performance from blends of karanja methyl ester and diesel. *Biomass Bioenerg.* 27(4): 393-397.
- Raja SA, Smart DSR, Lee CLR (2011). Biodiesel production from jatropha oil and its characterization. *Res. J. Chem. Sci.* 1(1): 81-87.
- Ramos MJ, Fernandez CM, Casas A, Rodriguez L, Perez A (2009). Influence of fatty acid composition of raw materials on biodiesel properties. *Bioresour. Technol.* 100(1): 261-268.
- Schuchardt U, Sercheli R, Vargas RM (1998). Transesterification of vegetable oils: a review. *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.* 9(3): 199-210. Shay EG (1993). Diesel fuel from vegetable oils: status and opportunities. *Biomass Bioenerg.* 4(4): 227-242.
- Shu Q, Yang B, Yuan H, Qing S, Zhu G (2007). Synthesis of biodiesel from soybean oil and methanol catalyzed by zeolite beta modified with La³⁺. *Catal Commun.* 8(12): 2159-2165.
- Veljkovic V, Lakicevic S, Stamenkovic O, Todorovic Z, Lazic M (2006). Biodiesel production from tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* L.) seed oil with a high content of free fatty acids. *Fuel*, 85(17-18): 2671-2675.
- Wang R, Hanna MA, Zhou WW, Bhadury PS, Chen Q, Song BA, Yang S (2011). Production and selected fuel properties of biodiesel from promising non-edible oils: *Euphorbia lathyris* L., *Sapium sebiferum* L. and *Jatropha curcas* L. *Bioresour. Technol.* 102(2): 1194-1199.
- Zhang J, Jiang L (2008). Acid-catalyzed esterification of *Zanthoxylum bungeanum* seed oil with high free fatty acids for biodiesel production. *Bioresour. Technol.* 99(18): 8995-8998.
- Zhang Y, Dube M, McLean D, Kates M (2003). Biodiesel production from waste cooking oil: 1. Process design and technological assessment. *Bioresour. Technol.* 89(1): 1-16.